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***Library in the Language Consciousness of Modern Students:
from a Book Depository to a Cultural and Educational Hub
(Based on a Free Associative Experiment)***

Objective. The purpose of the given paper is to record modern students' perception and interpretation of the *library* phenomenon, build associative field of the considered stimulus word, and analyze it in details. Basic options for the traditional and updated contextual compatibility of the lexeme *library* as an educational center, modern enlightening and cultural hub were presented and described in the article. **Methods.** In order to achieve the stated goal free associative experiment was conducted. General scientific methods of observation, comparison, generalization, description and systematization, as well as linguistic methods of linguistic observation and description were also utilized. **Results.** The results illustrate expansion of the connecting possibilities of the lexeme *library* and the transformation in its perception by Ukrainian and foreign students. **Conclusions.** The study proves that the interpretation of the *library* phenomenon by modern students doesn't contradict codified meaning of the lexeme under consideration. *Library* is associated with learning, reading literature, acquiring new knowledge, skills and abilities. At the same time, the concept of the library has been expanded to correlate it with a renewed space for studying, spending free time, holidays, organizing events, and communicating with acquaintances.

Keywords: associative experiment; associative field; linguistic consciousness; library; student

Introduction

The variability and rapid pace of global transformations that mark our modern world, in particular socio-economic modifications, displacement of traditional vectors of the development in current cultural and educational paradigms, information and technological progress, appearing fresh angels directions of the newest development for countries combining with large-scale changes in the field of international relations cause complete rejection of any international contacts, and expansion of cross-cultural contacts as well. Nowadays education system is changing, scaling and reformatting due to the strengthening of Ukraine's position in the international arena. All these significant changes are represented via language as an «universal characteristic of the human community, its core distinguishing feature» (Leshchenko & Zhovnir, 2018).

Significant changes indicate modern educational sector with all its institutions and subsidiary funds, including libraries. Basic format and role of them both in educational process and in students' lives outside the classroom is constantly changing. Recently, the boundaries of the traditional *library* interpretation have been expanding, which is primarily caused by extralinguistic factors. Traditional library sphere is varying, and the actualization of everything that correlates with it as an essential component of the contemporary lifestyle, education and growth in Ukraine are reflected in discourse.

From this standpoint, we believe that «layering of new contexts» on lexeme *library*, as well as its modernization and adaptation to current domestic and global socio-cultural processes, is considered as something meaningful and valid. Despite the fact that it is almost impossible to cover

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the lexical and semantic diversity in Ukrainian language and the changes in it (constant movement within the language paradigm prevents this), we derive attention and devote our exploration to the issue of reflecting *library* phenomenon in the linguistic consciousness of modern students as a driving force of progress and creators of the nearest future.

Objective. The purpose of the study is recording perception and interpretation of the *library* phenomenon by modern students, building associative field of the considered stimulus word, and its detailed analyzing. It was carried out with consideration of the respondents' subjective worldview projections.

The obtained results of the study will contribute to the formation of the general idea and perception of the modern library by students, who can be considered the main users of library services. Conclusions presented in the article will generally help to outline both achievements and possible shortcomings in the development of library science on the way to its transformation and rapid modernization. These considerations confirm the relevance and urgency of the proposed research, as well as its connection with the library sphere and information discourse.

Methods

To achieve the outlined goal, in particular to clarify the content of the lexeme *library* and to identify different meanings that were formed in students' minds, free associative experiment was conducted. Chosen way makes it possible to solve urgent problems of linguistics, because of its accessibility, simplified algorithm of conducting, and high degree of informativeness. At the stage of experiment preparation and its implementation different forms of conduct were taken into account, and written individual survey as the most rational one was chosen from among the spectrum of the evaluable relevant options. The given experiment provided an opportunity to emphasize on the key respondents' characteristics, denoted their individual features, experimental setup, etc.

In addition, general scientific methods of observation, comparison, generalization, description and systematization were applied in the article. They were used for the analysis and inventory of the actual material. The authors used proper linguistic methods, in particular method of linguistic observation and description. They were utilized for studying and lexeme explanation. It was done with a usage of dictionary thesaurus at the stage of arranging and presenting the results of the associative experiment. Basic elements of the method of quantitative calculations made it possible to carry out an accurate numerical parameterization of verbal representatives, namely the received word-reactions to the word-stimulus library.

The analyzed experiment was conducted in the spring and summer of 2024 and implemented in the form of an anonymous written survey of 70 respondents, particularly domestic and foreign medical students of the Poltava National Medical University (PDMU) and acquire the profession of a doctor. Taking into account the fact that students of PDMU come from different parts of Ukraine, as well as countries of other continents, primarily Africa, Asia, Europe, the geography of the experiment is quite extensive.

Results and Discussion

Linguistics reacts to the changes indicated above. It is primarily characterized by growing interest to the language study through its social value and extra lingual factors. Linguistic and conceptual pictures of the world are the core of modern cognitivism, separate branch of linguistics that studies thinking, perception, and cognition, as well as models' various processes and phenomena related to thinking and the multilevel reflection of reality. Cognitive linguistics is

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aimed at the analysis of mental processes that occur during the perception, understanding and interpretation of the surrounding realities by consciousness, involving consideration possible linguistic forms of the mental constructs representations and further analyzing of research results.

The procedure and theoretical foundations of conducting associative experiments are presented in the scientific studies of Ukrainian scientists (E. A. Vasyanovych, N. F. Balandina, O. I. Goroshko, O. V. Denisevich, O. F. Zagorodnya, T. V. Kuchma, U. B. Marchuk, T. E. Nedashkivska, Zh. P. Sokolovska, O. Ya. Surmach, K. V. Taranenko, D. I. Terekhova, O. M. Kholod, etc.), that had focused on topical problems of understanding the essence of the «alive meaning of the word», its identification and interpretation in the process of cognition and communication, delineating the specifics of contexts and interpreting a verbal. They also directed their research interest to the construction of associative fields, concepts for the reconstruction of fragments of linguistic and conceptual pictures the world. Thus, according to domestic researchers, it is the method of free associations that «proved itself excellently during the study of language consciousness, mentality and human lexicon» (Goroshko, Polyakova, & Zasiakin, 2024). At the same time, another Ukrainian linguist is convinced that «This experiment presupposes the access to respondents' consciousness, provoking the reactions to the stimulus», and «The associative experiment in linguistics aims to register responses, conditioned by information circulating within the participants' culture» (Lyubymova, 2020). So, «As a result of such experiments, an associative field as living, changing material, which combines the appropriate construct of lexical meaning and the connotative component, reflects the individual intuitive and emotional perception of reality by the speakers is formed» (Leshchenko & Zhovnir, 2023).

Theoretical and methodological basis of conducting associative experiments in the context of the psycholinguistic paradigm was built by foreign researchers, and domestic researchers strengthened and detailed it. Scientists directed their research potential to the study of the empirical component within cognitive research, urgent problems of reflection in the linguistic consciousness, cultural and behavioral stereotypes, individual stimulus words that correlate with key cultural and historical realities, verification of linguistic and sociocultural relevance and significance of key concepts, colors, ethnostereotypes, etc. (Holikova & Taranenko, 2022; Ding, Ding, Chen, & Shi, 2022; Kovalchuk & Litkovich, 2022; Lyubymova, 2020; Lewandowska-Tomaszczyk & Wilson, 2018; Semashko & Shvets, 2022; Semenova & Khristych, 2022); building associative fields of concepts (Goroshko, Polyakova, & Zasiakin, 2024; Pedchenko, 2023); studying various aspects within speech and language competence formation, language motivation, topical questions of linguistic didactics related to the language consciousness formation (Badenhorst, Martin, & Smolsik, 2023; Veivo, Porretta, Hyönä, & Järvikivi, 2018; Kalmykova, Kharchenko, Volzhentseva, Kalmykov, & Mysan, 2020; Liu et al., 2021).

Although there is no unified classification of verbal associations at this stage of language development, several variations of the principles and ways to analyze associates are currently functioning can be used. This is most likely determined by the excessive complexity of selecting universal parameters for the inventory, which would simultaneously take into account forms, contents, and types of associations. Instead, the parameterization of the associates obtained during the experiment was carried out devoting attention to various types of associative verbal connections, for example, syntagmatic associations, the grammatical class of which is different from the grammatical class of the stimulus word, and paradigmatic associations, which coincide according to the «grammatical class» criterion with the associate.

Obviously, it is not possible to draw a clear demarcation line between the existing criteria and principles of analysis and distribution of reactions, which indicates forming theoretical, methodological base and strengthening the already developed toolkit. For instance, there is a classification created by D. I. Terekhova, who suggested dividing reactions into syntagmatic,

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paradigmatic, thematic, phonetic, word-forming, grammatical, reminiscent, phraseological type, personalities (Terekhova, 2000).

Ukrainian researcher T. V. Kuchma offers her vision of current classifications, which are largely based on various principles and sometimes different essence interpretations, concept specificity and variety of the associative connection. From her point of view, it is necessary to distinguish such types, as syntagmatic (attributive, syntactic); paradigmatic (categorical, heteronymic, hyponymic, synonymous, antonymic); thematic; cognitive; phonetic; exclamatory; word-forming; reminiscent (quotes, names, characters from works of art, songs, movies, proverbs and sayings, etc.); personalities (names, 14 surnames of prominent people of the past and present) (Kuchma, 2013).

According to other scientists, associates should be divided by structure into the following: paradigmatic, syntagmatic, verbal compound, pictographic / thematic, word-forming, grammatical, phonetic, emotional-evaluative, reminiscent, proper names, abbreviations, non-verbal, complex, translation see the distribution of associates O. F. Zahorodnia (2018).

All existing classifications are an attempt to unify and organize the range of reflex words obtained during the associative experiment for the further reconstruction of the associative profile of images that can appear in consciousness. They integrate mental and sensory knowledge of a specific collective, community and ethnic group.

In this paper, we deal with the phenomenon of the *library* not by chance, since traditional library system have demonstrated the strong ability to change and respond to today's demands: «Public libraries in Ukraine adhere to the strategy of transition from a traditional book collection to a dynamic information center, which became possible thanks to organizational changes that took place against the background of large-scale implementation of information technologies in all production processes» (Chumak, 2022, p. 38).

It is essential that not only the informatization of public space and digitalization of educational and cultural spheres contributed to conceptual changes in the algorithm of libraries throughout the territory of Ukraine. Rapid updating of requirements, desire and the need to meet world standards, and compete with institutions of the same purpose, which provide services to different age categories of the population in European countries, have significantly expanded the spectrum of libraries. It means that basic informational and communicative functions were supplemented cultural, educational, and leisure ones have been added. At the same time, traditional information increasingly acquires features of information-analytical. Currently, libraries are actively interacting with people in various formats, providing continuous open and free access to information with its subsequent processing to various categories of the population, thus providing the needs of the modern reader.

According to researchers, library can position its image «1) as a place for creative work and study; 2) as a personal brand of an employee, if the individual is considered as a carrier of knowledge, professional skills, and talent; 3) through services to improve information literacy, conducting activities related to the provision of information products and services provided as a result of the library's information research; 4) through the collection of the library fund; 5) using the website, pages in social networks, and media content produced by the library» (Vasylynyna, Derevianko, & Doroshenko, 2022, p. 162).

All mentioned above confirms relevance of the chosen topic and its timeliness, hence modification of the *library* as a phenomenon in the linguistic consciousness of society, primarily its active users are strengthening.

Working in libraries with the existing library fund and all its attributes appears as a specific process, formed over a long period of time, and it is fixed in speech an in written discourse. We assume that at the level of the students' everyday consciousness *library* is considered as familiar

item, a routine part of the educational process, something that is an attribute of higher education, an element of student life. It's also correlates with the process to acquire new knowledge, and to form general and professional skills or abilities. This quite likely complements the axiological paradigm of modern youth.

Analysis of the Ukrainian language defining dictionaries shows a picture of the extensive lexicographic fixation of the term *library*. As of now, it is codified with the following interpretations: «1. An institution, a cultural institution, where books, magazines, etc. are stored and issued to readers, as well as popularization and promotion of literary works. 2. A more or less significant number of books specially selected for reading, scientific work, for the purpose of collecting, etc. 3. Premises, room for storing books; book store 4. The name of related serial publications or books or magazines intended for a certain category of readers» (*Slovnyk Ukrayins'koyi Movy*, vol. 1, p. 173). In the dictionary register, we record the lexeme library-reading room, which is interpreted as «library in which there is a hall or a room where you can get and read books, magazines, newspapers, etc.; Public library see public» (*Slovnyk Ukrayins'koyi Movy*, vol. 1, p. 173). As for the adjectival part of the phrase public given above, it is codified with the meaning «Designed for wide attendance, use; public» (*Slovnyk Ukrayins'koyi Movy*, vol. 7, p. 373).

Dictionaries record the primary meaning of any term / concept. Such a meaning is unequivocal and devoid of individuality of semantics. Even though lexicographic sources reflect array of collectively acquired knowledge they don't take into account either personal, behavioral, or mental intentional layering. We consider valid the reasoning of the domestic researcher Ya. Yaremko, who notes: «no matter how accurate the dictionary definition is, it is not able to verbally reproduce the deep meaning acquired by the denotation in the process of conceptualizing reality» (Yaremko, 2012-2013, p. 7). For a more accurate understanding, it is necessary to involve the associative background, which actualizes the connotative, axiological, and stylistic plans of meaning. It is impossible to create correct picture of the current language space without taking into account basic peculiarities of the modern word usage, and devoting attention to the probable changes in its meaning.

It becomes obvious that the considered definitions explicate a number of relevant signs to indicate what correlates with the essence and functional direction of the considered cultural and educational institutions, in particular the collection and storage of printed and handwritten materials, their cataloging for the readers service readers' both in the premises of the institution and outside its limits.

There is no mention of the availability of electronic resources in the library fund and the possibility of using them, which is explained by the recent change in the range of services offered by librarians and its traditional format. Descriptive characteristics are strengthened by possible contexts, because the presentation of probable word combinations makes it possible to understand the exact semantic structure of the word with its subtle shades of meaning. This can replace the absence of non-verbal characteristics in dictionaries, as it appeals to the empirical component of meaning.

Modern interpretation and syntagmatic connections of the lexeme *library* in Ukrainian linguistic culture don't contradict its codified interpretation, although they do not match the definitions available in the dictionary thesaurus. At the same time its connecting capabilities have been expanded due to the appearance and entry into active usage of nominations such as *bibliothub* (*library hub*), *library space*, *library point*, *library co-working*, *library mainstream*, *library lesson*, *library forum*, *library tool*, etc. They have significant functional pragmatic weight in our time.

For the time being, *library* determines the widest possible modern social space and is overgrown with new contexts. It could be considered as a communicatively relevant and actively

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used concept. Compounds are becoming established that reflect modern Ukrainian cultural and educational realities. There is an urgent need to verbally record the mentioned changes and renovation within domestic cultural and educational segments.

Updating in the student's minds, including younger generation, lexeme *library* is increasingly associated with a multi-format hub containing a complex of various types of information on traditional and modern media. The connecting habits of words are also changing. After detailed analyzing of the connecting potential of the considered lexeme *library* we suggest to divide all the contexts that had been found in the discursive space into traditional and non-traditional (modern).

Traditional contexts are *national, children's, school / university, village, city, district, old, new, beautiful, powerful, scientific, popular, public, public, generally available, special, specialized, etc. marked by a desire for the usual, time-tested, unchanging, instead modernized options, for example, modernized, multifunctional, mobile, digital, video, audio, transformed, eco, open, electronic, media, web, cyber, gaming, virtual, etc.* They reflect present extra lingual changes, explain the dynamism of extra-linguistic / language systems, thereby confirming their monolithic unity. It is noteworthy that both contexts coexist in the same discursive plane. They should not be contrasted, and logically considered not separately, but in a complex.

In order to fix discrepancy between current and classical interpretation of the *library* as a cultural and educational center, and to reveal possible differences between the real meaning of the lexeme and the traditional one recorded in dictionaries, we conducted a free association experiment. It made it possible to investigate the consciousness of modern education seekers on the material of language and to draw conclusions about actual, «living» representations of the considered phenomenon in the minds of young people.

It is well known that primary lexical associations are the result of spontaneous, unprepared, and therefore as close as possible to reality, intentional reactions of the respondents. Such associations can be seen as an associative profile of consciousness that integrates mental and sensory collective knowledge. Free associative experiment was chosen to reveal key reflective peculiarities of the concept *library* in the students' language consciousness.

The age and gender of the interviewees were not determining factors; therefore, they were indicated in the questionnaires at will. These data did not affect the processing of the results, conclusions and generalizations. The recorded answers outline the approximate age range of the experiment participants was from 18 to 27 years old.

The parameters of the respondents regarding their possible previous education, acquired profession, qualification, place of birth and permanent residence are different, but these data are not recorded directly in the questionnaires, since they do not significantly affect the nature of the survey results and, therefore, are not relevant for our study. The key factor in the selection of respondents is studying at a higher educational institution at the time of the survey.

The experiment had face-to-face (direct contact with respondents) and face-to-face (sending questionnaires by regular and e-mail, involvement of messengers) form, which made it possible to attract a domestic contingent of students, as well as foreign students who, despite the full-scale war, continue to study in Ukraine in a mixed format.

Attention was devoted to the instruction; hence respondents were informed about the essence and specifics of the procedure. In addition to this, key points of the action algorithm were explained in detail. It was emphasized that everyone should reproduce the primary associations embedded and appeared on a fly in the subconscious, because they are considered to be the closest to real and the most illustrative. According to the methodology of the free experiment, any restrictions in terms of meaning or form were leveled, and a few seconds were allotted for writing

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the word-reaction. Informants focused on the fact that the result will not be evaluated from the position of right / wrong, because there is no single exemplary option or set of best / worst.

Since the participants of the experiment included foreigners, it was emphasized that it is impractical to take into account possible language errors or other mistakes, and to facilitate the perception of the task the original version of the questionnaire was duplicated in English. It was necessary to provide respondents with optimal electronic translator to present the exact Ukrainian equivalent of the verbal reflex in English, but no additional time was allocated for this.

It is interesting and important that foreign students had studied at the university offline and were active users of the updated library fund of the city before the war started. Some of them used the reading rooms and subscriptions of the Poltava Regional Universal Scientific Library named after I. Kotlyarevsky / Poltava Regional Library for Youth named after Olesya Honchara. Before the start of the experiment it was emphasized the need to record primary verbal reactions specifically to the libraries of Ukraine, since traditional cultural and educational institutions of similar purpose in their Motherland may differ in their concept and range of services from those operating in Ukraine.

The structure of the questionnaire (Table 1) has the following parts: introductory and main. The introductory part is an address to the respondent, in which the purpose of the research is defined, the significance of the role of the respondent for its achievement is emphasized. This motivates the respondent, causes the desire to answer the questions of the questionnaire and join the experiment in general. Among the personal data in the questionnaire is information about age, gender and place of residence (optional elements). The second block contains tasks. The questionnaire ends with a thank you to each respondent for their participation and attention to the idea.

Table 1

<p>Анкета / Questionnaire Шановні студенти! / Dear students!</p> <p>Для участі в опитуванні просимо записати найперші словесні реакції на слово <i>бібліотека</i> / To participate in the survey please write down the first verbal reactions to the word <i>бібліотека (library)</i>. Ваші відповіді є надзвичайно цінними для експерименту / Your answers are extremely valuable for the experiment. Найперші асоціації до слова в <i>бібліотека</i> / First associations to the word <i>бібліотека (library)</i>:</p> <p>_____</p> <p>Вік / Age _____ Місце проживання / Residence _____</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Щиро дякуємо за ваші відповіді! / Thank you so much for your answers!</p>
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The most frequent received reactions informants used in their everyday communication, because of this fact they were spontaneously produced by consciousness and accordingly verbalized. All fixed results explain the prevalence of the considered units in the interviewed group. Later, they were systematized and presented in the table «The center and core of the associative field of the word library» (Table 2).

In total, the stimulus word library received 253 reactions, 56 of which were excellent (22%). According to part-language affiliation noun reactions prevail and get 180 (71.2%) of the total number. During the calculation of the quantitative results of the received verbal reflexes 38 verbs, 14 adjectives, and 12 adverbs were recorded, which is 15%, 5.5%, and 4.8% of their total

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number. At the syntactic level 9 (5.5%) of reactions to the stimulus *library* were reflected by word combinations.

Respondents had no difficulty with the proposed stimulus, so refusals to write answers were not presented. It should be noted that several responses were submitted in English. Presumably, the explanation for this is the impossibility of foreign students who participated in the proposed experiment pick up the Ukrainian equivalent of the word that was formed in their minds in their native language to quickly and accurately. There is one picture (an image of a heart) among the responses of the respondents.

The core of the associative field includes underlined reaction words. Numbers highlighted in bold in the table indicate reflexive words that are close in meaning. Single associations located on the periphery of the associative field. However, they are valuable for its validity of the obtained results, but were not presented in the table (Table 2).

Table 2

Library Book / books / books / a book / books – 33 reactions (13%) Training – 23 reactions (9%) Knowledge – 19 responses (7.5%)
To study – 12 reactions Librarian – 12 reactions The score – 9 reactions Friends – 9 reactions To read – 9 reactions To learn – 9 reactions To cram – 8 reactions Classroom – 7 reactions Computer – 6 reactions Ukraine – 5 reactions Ukrainian language – 5 reactions School – 5 reactions Pair – 5 reactions Magazine – 5 reactions Boring – 4 reactions Event – 4 reactions Tables / desks – 4 reactions To sleep – 4 reactions Quiet – 4 reactions Holiday – 3 reactions Space – 3 reactions Take it easy – 3 reactions Ukrainian – 3 reactions Mom – 2 reactions Lamp – 2 reactions Tense – 2 reactions Internet – 2 reactions Repair – 2 reactions Beautiful – 2 reactions Interesting – 2 reactions New – 2 reactions To sleep – 2 reactions PDMU – 2 reactions Silence – 2 reactions Coffee – 2 reactions

Results shows that library is thought to have associations with books, studying, learning and acquiring new knowledge, and therefore it couldn't be separated from development and self-improvement. This confirm the verbal reflexes *book / books / book / books, learning, knowledge*, which form the core of the associative field of the phenomenon under consideration. Instead of it the center and periphery illustrate expansion of a typical, mainly stereotypical idea of it.

Semantically close and connotatively neutral verbal reactions were used to denote such meaning as «Learn, master, try to remember». Some samples were recorded as frequently used associates. They are *to study, to study / to study* – 9 reactions, *to study* – 8 reactions, *to study* – 4 reactions. All mentioned thoughts should be interpreted as having a positive connotation and indicating the primary and most common purpose of the library, particularly providing users' requests in order to obtain necessary for learning information, providing free access to it on various media and resources, creating an atmosphere for working with the literary fund.

Reflexes that nominate subjects of the library space, educational disciplines that are mandatory to be studied by students, their attributes to the library discourse in general are quite expected: *office* – 7 reactions, *computer* – 6 reactions, *tables / desks* – 4 reactions, *space* – 3 reactions, *PDMU* – 2 reactions, *repair* – 2 reactions, *lamp* – 2 reactions, *coffee* – 2 reactions, *Internet* – 1 reaction, *biochemistry* – 1 reaction, *lunch* – 1 reaction. Some of the given answers illustrate fragments of individual perception of the concept of *library*.

Recorded reflexes illustrate usual attributes of the library and working there in general. They correlate with open access to literature, information, and documentation for further processing / use according to a previously outlined intention, for example, *to prepare for a class, complete an assignment, read a book, process a magazine article, write a synopsis, take a test on a computer, etc.*

Associate *Ukraine* was recorded in questionnaires of some respondents. Most likely, this answer was given by foreign students. The reason for this is that some of them became familiar with traditional and electronic Ukrainian library funds, including those that are located in the educational institution. They started to use literature, computers, or Internet resources in the reading rooms of the regional libraries. Hence, library became a place where foreign students studied Ukrainian language as a foreign, deepen information about Ukraine and Ukrainians, its culture, customs, life, leisure, mental characteristics as representatives of a separate ethnic community. They spent a lot of time there like Ukrainian students did. sometimes couples were spent Some classes were held in the library premises, which confirms the presence of an associate *class* (1 reaction). A recorded nomenclature of *absenteeism* (1 response) indicates that auditory time was spent in the library space.

The connotational fragment of the associative meaning is determined by an individual and personal factor. These can be feelings that arise / arose during a stay in the library, dealing with educational and scientific literature, discussing important questions and problems, consulting, working at a computer or talking with friends. The *library* stimulus evoked associates containing polar evaluative reactions, inter alia: positive and negative. Examples of this include *quiet* – 4 reactions, *calm* – 3 reactions, *new, beautiful, interesting* – 2 reactions each, *safe, beautiful* – 1 reaction each). Meantime, we fixed few negatively marked lexemes, specifically *boring* – 5 reactions, *tense* – 2 reactions.

Yet, at the same time, *library* is associated with not pleasant but obligatory process that is verbalized by the lexeme *cramming* – 6 reactions (used to denote «Repeating something many times, learning by heart, without thinking about the content» (*Slovnyk Ukrayins'koyi Movy*, vol. 7, p. 373). A similar attitude towards the institution under consideration is explained by the associations *sleep* – 4 and 2 reactions respectively. Such fixations are marked negatively, and they are convinced that in the linguistic consciousness of the students there is an idea of tedious work

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in the library as something forced, uninteresting, but necessary for certain objective / subjective reasons.

The phrase *Ukrainian language* was recorded in the questionnaires of 5 respondents, which may indicate both the importance of the discipline in the educational process and the need to visit library / use the fund to prepare assignments, study literature on the Ukrainian, etc. Instead, the phrases *new renovation*, *the smell of books*, *smart people*, *Ukrainian language teacher* are located on the periphery. Such reactions are considered as a part of the general associative and verbal grid obtained during the experiment. It reproduced individual worldview of the particular respondents. Personal projection of the library's subjective perception of the world is reflected in unique (sometimes single) reactions. Examples of this include *mother* – 2 reactions, *monitor* – 1 reaction. Their origin is difficult to explain.

It is gratifying that a group of associates, inter alia: *event* – 4 reactions, a *holiday* – 3 reactions, a *bookcrossing* – 1 reaction confirm current implementation of the educational and enlightening function of the modern *libraries*. It shows that such spaces are literary becoming centers of out-of-classroom activities and events organized for students or held with their participation.

The associative field of the lexeme library is presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Conclusions

The language system is constantly developing. This process is reflected at all its levels, primarily at the lexical and semantic level. Meaning of words changes gradually. It expands or narrows. Changing realities determines manipulation of the available lexical resource at the level of verbal use. Fragments of social reality are reflected in language, which correlate with the change in the concept and functions of the traditional library. This fact has a significant impact on the

communicative status of derivatives of the word *library* and those semantically close to it, in particular new ones are in active use by native speakers of the Ukrainian language, while traditional ones are partially relegated to the periphery.

According to the results of the conducted associative experiment, we note that the associative meaning of the stimulus *library* is formed in the minds of modern students by a complex of semantically close nuclear reactions, namely *book / books / books / a book / books, study, knowledge*. They do not contradict its lexicographic definition, and convince that the library remains a place associated with learning, acquiring new knowledge, skills and abilities through the use of literature, in particular reading books.

At the same time, we can conclude that the library is beginning to be associated with a renewed space for studying, spending free time and communicating with friends. This is convincing in further transformations of the considered concept.

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Бібліотека в мовній свідомості сучасного здобувача освіти: від книгозбірні до культурно-освітнього хабу (на матеріалі вільного асоціативного експерименту)

Мета праці – фіксація сприйняття й інтерпретації феномену бібліотека сучасними студентами й вибудовування та аналіз асоціативного поля розглядуваного слова-стимулу з урахуванням проєкцій суб'єктивного світосприйняття респондентів. Крім цього, у статті було подано й описано варіанти традиційної та оновленої контекстуальної сполучуваності лексеми бібліотека як освітньо-навчального осередку, так і просвітницько-культурного хабу. **Методика.** Для досягнення мети було проведено вільний асоціативний експеримент, а також застосовано загальнонаукові методи спостереження, зіставлення, узагальнення, опису й систематизації та власне лінгвістичні методи – лінгвістичного спостереження й опису. **Результати** ілюструють розширення сполучуваних можливостей лексеми бібліотека і трансформації у її сприйманні студентами. **Висновки.** Дослідження доводить те, що інтерпретація феномена бібліотека сучасними здобувачами освіти не суперечить кодифікованому значенню розглядуваної лексеми. У свідомості студентів бібліотека асоціюється з навчанням, опрацюванням літератури, здобуванням нових знань, умінь і навичок. Водночас уявлення про бібліотеку розширено до співвіднесення її з оновленим простором для навчання, проведення вільного часу, свят, івентів, спілкування з друзями.

Ключові слова: асоціативний експеримент; асоціативне поле; мовна свідомість; бібліотека; здобувач освіти

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